

Mental Health Assessment of Teaching and Non-teaching Employees at the University of Jammu

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The objective of this research was to examine the mental health status of the participants. A 2x2 factorial design consisting of two independent variables has been employed in the present study. The sample consists of 80 subjects. The first independent variable, i.e., gender has been divided into two categories: male and female. The second independent variable employees have been divided into two categories, i.e., teaching and non-teaching. Mental health, in the present context, is taken up as a dependent variable. For collecting the data, we have applied the MHS (Mental Health Scale) constructed by Sharma. It has 60 statements (30 positive, 30 negative). The result of this study indicates that gender is not found to be a significant factor, while employees are an important factor in this study. The findings suggest that teaching staff exhibit better mental health compared to non-teaching employees, and the differences in results are thoroughly discussed, with potential explanations provided.

Keywords: Mental health, factorial design, consisting, employees, significant

Mental health refers to an individual's emotional, cognitive, and behavioral well-being, enabling them to function effectively in daily life, manage stress, maintain relationships, and make rational decisions. It is not just the absence of mental disorders but the presence of positive mental functions. In psychological terms, good mental health allows an individual to maintain a stable sense of self, effectively interact with others, and engage in meaningful activities while experiencing minimal psychological distress. According to Freud (2019), mental health is defined in terms of an individual's ability to manage internal conflicts, maintain a balance between different aspects of personality, and adapt to reality effectively. Freud's psychoanalytic theory suggests that mental health is achieved when the id, ego, and superego are in harmony, allowing a person to function well in their personal and social life. A well-known statement attributed to Freud regarding mental health is: "To be mentally healthy is to be able to love and to work." This implies that a mentally healthy individual can form meaningful relationships, love and engage in productive activities and work without excessive psychological distress. He believed that unresolved unconscious conflicts could lead to mental disorders, and psychoanalysis aimed to bring these conflicts to awareness for resolution. According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition, Text Revision (DSM-5-TR) provides a comprehensive framework for diagnosing and understanding mental disorders. It defines mental disorders as "a syndrome characterized by clinically significant disturbance in an individual's cognition, emotion regulation, or behavior that reflects a dysfunction in the psychological, biological, or developmental processes underlying mental functioning" (American Psychiatric Association, 2022). The World Health Organization extends this understanding by defining mental health as "a state of well-being in

which an individual realizes his or her abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively, and can contribute to his or her community" (World Health Organization, 2022). An employee is defined as an individual who engages in structured work within an organization and is influenced by psychological factors such as motivation, job satisfaction, stress, and interpersonal relationships. Workplace psychology studies employee behavior, productivity, and well-being, emphasizing aspects such as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, leadership impact, work-life balance, and organizational commitment (Maslow, 1943; Herzberg, 1959). According to the American Psychological Association (APA), gender is: A complex set of characteristics and behaviors that are culturally associated with an individual's sex, including gender identity (a person's deeply held sense of their gender) and gender expression (how they present their gender to others).

In conclusion, mental health is a multidimensional concept that extends beyond the absence of mental illness and includes the presence of positive psychological functioning, emotional stability, and effective social interaction. It enables individuals to cope with everyday challenges, maintain meaningful relationships, and perform their professional responsibilities effectively. Within organizational settings, psychological factors such as motivation, job satisfaction, stress, and interpersonal relationships play an important role in shaping an employee's overall well-being and work performance.

In institutional environments where individuals perform diverse roles and responsibilities, maintaining good mental health becomes essential for sustaining productivity, cooperation, and a positive work atmosphere. Differences in job demands, work environments, and role expectations may influence the psychological well-being of employees in different ways. Therefore, examining mental health within such professional settings can provide valuable insights into the factors that support employee well-being and contribute to a healthier and more efficient organizational environment.

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Objectives of the Study

- To study the effect of Gender on mental health.
- To study the effect of teaching and nonteaching employees on mental health.

- To study the interaction between gender and employees on mental health.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There will be no statistically significant difference in the mental health scores between male and female participants.
- No notable difference is expected in the mental health scores among the employees.
- There will be no significant interaction between the gender and employees.

Method

Participants

Total 80 subjects (40 males & 40 females) employees working in teaching and non-teaching positions were randomly selected as participants from the University of Jammu, J&K. The age of the participants ranged from 35 to 55 years.

Experimental Design

A 2x2 factorial design consisting of two independent variables, namely gender and employees, is used. The dependent variable is mental health in the present study.

Measures

Mental Health Scale (MHS) constructed by Sharma (2002) is used to measure the mental health of the employees. The scale has demonstrated robust reliability, with test-retest reliability coefficients reported at 0.86 and split-half reliability at 0.88. Validity assessments have yielded a coefficient of 0.79, indicating good construct validity. While the scale does not explicitly label specific factors or subscales, the content of the items suggests that it measures aspects such as: Behavioral Attributes: Assessing actions and conduct in various situations. Intellectual and Academic Status: Evaluating cognitive functions and performance in educational settings. Anxiety Levels: Measuring feelings of worry, nervousness, or unease. Social Popularity: Gauging acceptance and likability among peers. Happiness and Satisfaction: Assessing overall contentment and fulfillment in life.

Data Collection

The work of data collection has been done on the employees (teaching & nonteaching) of the University of Jammu, Jammu. First, "rapport" was established with the subjects individually. The subjects are instructed, and the mental health scale is given to the subjects individually. A proper and peaceful environment is created for the commencement of the test. The subject is asked to read out the instructions and statements printed on the scale carefully and put the right mark in the box against the option that applies best to the subject.

However, there is no time limit to file it, even then you are suggested to complete it at the earliest possible. After ensuring the subject is satisfied, the scale is given to fill, and the subject is returned the same, when he has completed it. Following this procedure, the data are collected from all the subjects selected in the study.

Scoring: There are 60 statements in the mental health scale, three options of each statement are also given (Yes, Undecided, No) The scheme of scoring is on positive statement 2 marks for "yes", 1 mark

for "undecided" and 0 mark for "no", and for negative statements adopt just reverse making 2 marks for "no", 1 mark for "undecided" and 0 mark for "yes".

Data Analysis

Two-way analyses of variances have been used to analysis the data.

Results and Discussion

The aim of this research was to examine the impact of two independent variables i.e. Gender and Employees on mental health. After collecting data, the two-way analysis of variance as statistical technique is employed.

The summary table analysis of variance is given below.

Table 1

Summary Table if ANOVA

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	MS	"F" Ratio
Gender (A)	90.31	1	90.31	0.742
Employee (B)	11592.11	1	11592	95.28*
Interaction (A X B)	3.61	1	3.61	0.862
Error	9246.15	76	121.65	
Total	20932.18	79		

Note. *Denotes significant at .01 level of confidence.

A close examination of the summary table of the analysis of variance reveals that employees in teaching and non-teaching roles have a significant effect on mental health. This indicates that the nature of employment plays a crucial role in influencing mental health.

Interaction Plot: Gender and Employee Type on Mental Health

The interaction plot above shows the mean mental health scores for male and female employees across teaching and non-teaching roles:

- The blue solid line represents male employees, showing a sharp decline from teaching to non-teaching roles.
- The red dashed line represents female employees, showing a more gradual decline.
- There is no strong interaction effect, as the lines do not cross significantly. However, the effect of employment type is notable, with teaching roles associated with higher mean scores, especially for males.

Table 2

Mean Table (Employees)

Employee	N	Total	Mean
Teaching	40	3071	76.78
Non-Teaching	40	2111	52.78

The table of means as well as the graph values indicate that subjects in teaching roles exhibit higher mental health scores compared to those in non-teaching roles. This finding suggests that employment type significantly influences the mental health of employees at the University of Jammu.

Table 3

Mean Table (Gender)

Gender	N	Total	Mean
Male	40	2635	65.88
Female	40	2550	63.75

The table of mean values as well as graph show that the males and Females have been found to have a minor level of difference, i.e., 2.13 it means that Gender has no statistically significant effect on the mental health scores.

The finding of the study is supported by the results obtained by many investigators Anand (1989) observed that male teachers were mentally healthy than those of female teachers, the state of working bears no relation to mental health while social values were positively related to mental health of teachers Bhagi and Sharma (1992), Singh and Walia (2004), and Kaur (2007), Srivastava and Khan (2008) concluded that male teachers perceived emotional well-being, relatively freedom from anxiety, and a capacity to establish constructive relationships and to cope with ordinary demands and stresses of life than the female teachers. Zilli et al. (2009) concluded that the female youth scored higher on mental health dimensions as compared to their male counterparts. Purunima (2012) found that the mental health of male teachers is higher than that of female teachers (Nahar et al., 2013). A number of researchers have explored how job-related stress influences mental health across different employment

sectors. One such investigation involved 100 participants, evenly divided between government and private sector employees. The results demonstrated a significant positive link between job stress and the nature of employment. Additionally, a negative relationship was identified between job satisfaction and gender.

In a study by Bashie et al. (2015) teachers evaluated their experiences related to the quality of work life in schools. While they rated their work life as moderately satisfactory, their psychological well-being levels were reported to be relatively high. The findings also highlighted that certain demographic factors affected how teachers perceived their work environment. Akbari-Zardkhaneh, Srinivasan, and their team (2018) researched college educators, revealing that teachers' strong mental health positively impacts students' learning experiences and overall outlook on life. Conversely, students may also influence teachers' mental health, indicating a two-way relationship. Kumar (2019) in his study titled "Mental Health at the Workplace: A Study on Non-Teaching Staff in the University Campus," evaluated general health aspects of non-teaching university staff. The focus was particularly on issues like social dysfunction and symptoms of depression. An article from the International Journal of Indian Psychology (2019) titled "Stress Management among Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff," examined how both groups manage stress. The study found that non-teaching employees demonstrated better stress management capabilities compared to their teaching colleagues. A more recent study by researchers at Jouf University, Saudi Arabia (2023) investigated mental health issues and coping mechanisms among university staff, particularly non-teaching personnel, during the COVID-19 pandemic. It provided valuable insights into how the pandemic affected mental well-being and highlighted strategies used for psychological resilience. In 2024, a study conducted by Halat, Sami, Soltani, and Malki (2024) conducted a study on Mental health interventions affecting university faculty: a systematic review and meta-analysis. This study critically appraised the effectiveness of interventions designed to improve the mental health of university faculty. Alif, Sultana, Salehin, and colleagues (2024) conducted a study on staff working at higher education institutions, This study identified factors associated with job insecurity, burnout, psychological distress, and coping among staff at higher education institutions globally.

Conclusion

This research paper explores the fundamental factors that define mental health, the importance of maintaining psychological resilience, and strategies for promoting long-term well-being. Mental health is shaped by multiple biological, psychological, social, and environmental factors. These factors can either support mental well-being or contribute to the development of mental health disorders. Research and observations indicate that teaching staff generally have better mental health compared to non-teaching employees. This difference may be attributed to factors such as greater job recognition, opportunities for professional growth, and more structured work roles. On the other hand, non-teaching staff often deal with high workloads, lower job autonomy, and limited career advancement, contributing to higher stress levels and poorer mental well-being. Mental health is a critical factor in the overall well-being and productivity of both teaching and non-teaching employees in educational institutions. Teachers often face stress due to workload, student behavior, and administrative demands, while

non-teaching staff experience pressures related to management, maintenance, and support roles. Both groups require targeted mental health support to ensure a healthy and effective work environment.

Promoting mental well-being through counseling services, stress management programs, and a positive workplace culture can significantly enhance job satisfaction, reduce burnout, and improve overall institutional efficiency. Educational institutions need to foster an environment that prioritizes mental health, encouraging open discussions and implementing proactive strategies to support all employees. By doing so, they can create a more resilient and motivated workforce, ultimately benefiting students and the broader educational community.

To bridge this gap and enhance mental health for non-teaching employees, institutions should implement supportive measures, including:

Workplace Well-being Programs: Regular mental health workshops, counseling services, and wellness initiatives.

Fair Workload Distribution: Ensuring equitable workloads to reduce stress and prevent burnout.

Recognition and Career Growth: Providing training, skill development, and promotion opportunities to enhance job satisfaction.

Supportive Work Environment: Encouraging open communication, peer support, and management involvement in addressing mental health concerns.

Flexible Work Policies: Offering reasonable work schedules, breaks, and leave options to maintain work-life balance.

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